

On Intuitionistic Fuzzy Neutrosophic Soft Ideal Topological Spaces

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to introduce the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal in Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set theory. The concept of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft local function is also introduced. These concepts are discussed with a view to find new intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies from the original one. The basic structure, respectively a basic for such generated Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies also studied here. Finally, the notion of compatibility of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft

ideals with Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies is introduced and some equivalent conditions concerning, this topic are established here.

Keywords: *Fuzzy soft set, Neutrosophic soft, Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal, Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft local function, Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology, compatible Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal.*

Introduction

The fuzzy set was presented by Zadeh in 1965 where every element had a degree of membership (Zadeh, 1965). Intuitionistic fuzzy set as generalized fuzzy set is quite interesting and useful in many application areas was introduced by Atanassov, K. (1983; 1994; 1999), Szmidt, E., & Kacprzyk, J. (2001; 2004). The idea of Neutrosophic set presented by F. Smarandache (1998) which is a mathematical instrument for dealing with issues including uncertain, indeterminacy and conflicting

information. The concept of a soft sets was introduced by Molodtsov (1999). Initialed the theory of soft sets as a new mathematical tool for dealing with uncertainties. Maji (2013) had joined the Neutrosophic set with delicate sets and presented another scientific model "Neutrosophic soft set". A new notion of Fuzzy Neutrosophic soft set and its basic operations and results in Fuzzy Neutrosophic soft space are obtained. Kuuratowski (1996) and Vaidyanathaswamy (1944) introduced the concept of ideal in topological space and defined local function in ideal topological space. Further

Hamlrtt and Jankovic (1990) studied the properties of ideal topological space. Szmidt, E., & Kacprzyk, J. (2001) defined intuitionistic fuzzy ideal for a set and generalized the concept of fuzzy ideal concepts, first initiated by Sarkar, D. (1997). Also, i Salama, A. A., Smarandache, F., & Alblowi, S. A. (2014) introduced and studied the concept of Neutrosophic crisp local function, and construct a new type of Neutrosophic crisp topological space Via Neutrosophic crisp ideals . the concept of Fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal topological space introduced by Lafta, A.F., Mohammed, J. & Ayed, E. (2019).

The purpose behind this paper is to present the ideal of intuitionistic Fuzzy neutrosophic Soft ideal in intuitionistic Fuzzy neutrosophic soft set theory which is the generalization of concept of intuitionistic Fuzzy ideal topological concept and soft ideal topological concepts, first initiated by Jassim, M. & Salman, W. (2015), Kandil et al. (2014) sequentially.

The concept of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft local function is also introduced. These ideas are talked about so as to discover new intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies from the original one. The basic structure, especially a basis for such generated intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies also studied here .The notion of compatibility of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideals with intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal topologies is introduced and some equivalent conditions concerning this topic are established here.

Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. (Arockiarani, & Jency, 2014): A Fuzzy neutrosophic set A on the universe X is defined as $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle ; x \in X \}$ where the function $T, I, F: X \rightarrow [0,1]$. Denote the degree of indet the degree membership function $T, I, F: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ denoted the degree of indet the degree of membership function (namely $T_A(x)$), the degree of indeterminacy function (namely $I_A(x)$) and the degree of non-membership (namely

$F_A(x)$) respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A and $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$

Definition 2.2. (Kandil et al., 2014): Let X be a universe set and E be a set of paramters . A pair (F,E) is called a soft set over X if and only if F is a function from E into the set of all in to the set of all subsets of X ,i.e. $F: E \rightarrow p(x)$ where $p(x)$ is the power set of X . The set of all soft sets over X is denoted by $SS(X, E)$.

Definition 2.3. (Atanassov, 1986): An intuitionistic fuzzy set A over the universe set X can be defined as follows $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle ; x \in X \}$

Where the function $\mu_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\nu_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ with the property $0 \leq \mu(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$ The value $\mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x)$ represent the degree of member ship of x to A respectively.

Definition 2.4. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic set A on the universe of discourse U is defined as $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), I_A(x) \rangle , x \in U \}$ where $\min[F_A, T_A(x)] \leq 0.5, \min[I_A, T_A(x)] \leq 0.5, \min[F_A, I_A(x)] \leq 0.5$, for all $x \in U$ with the condition $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + (x) \leq 2$

Definition 2.5. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let U be an initial universe set. Let E be a set of parameters and a non-empty set $A \subset E$.

Let $IFN(U)$ denotes the set of all intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic set of U . The pair (F, A) is called intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set (in short IFNSS) over U , where F is mapping given by $F: A \rightarrow IFN(U)$ and $IFNSS(F, A)$ is denoted by $\tilde{F}_A$

Definition 2.6. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be a set of parameters. The Not set of E is denoted by $\neg E$ is defined as $E = \{ \neg e_1, \neg e_2, \dots, \neg e_n \}$ where $\neg e_i = \text{not } e_i, \forall i$.

Definition 2.7. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): The complement of an intuitionistic Fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_A$ is denoted by $(\tilde{F}_A)^c$

and is defined as $\tilde{F}_A^c = (F^c, \neg A)$ where $\tilde{F}_A^c: \neg A \rightarrow IFN(U)$ is a mapping given by $\tilde{F}_A^c(e) = \text{intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft complement with } T_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x) = F_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x) = I_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x)$ and $F_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x) = T_{\tilde{F}_A^c(e)}(x) \forall x \in U, \forall e \in \neg A$.

Definition 2.8. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_A$ over U is said to be empty intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set with respect to the parameter A if

$$T_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 0, I_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 0, F_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 1 \quad \forall e \in A, \forall x \in U. \text{ It is denoted by } \tilde{0}_A$$

Thus, we have

$$T_{\tilde{0}_A(e)}(x) = 0, I_{\tilde{0}_A(e)}(x) = 0, F_{\tilde{0}_A(e)}(x) = 1$$

Definition 2.9. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_A$ over U is said to be the universe intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set with respect to the parameter A if

$$T_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 1, I_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 0, F_{\tilde{F}_A(e)}(x) = 0 \quad \forall e \in A, \forall x \in U. \text{ It is denoted by } \tilde{1}_A$$

Thus, we have

$$T_{\tilde{1}_A(e)}(x) = 1, I_{\tilde{1}_A(e)}(x) = 0, F_{\tilde{1}_A(e)}(x) = 0$$

Note: $(\tilde{0}_A)^c = \tilde{1}_A$ and $(\tilde{1}_A)^c = \tilde{0}_A$

Definition 2.10. (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): 1) An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_A$ over U is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point, denoted by $e_{\tilde{F}_A}$, if for the element

$e \in E, \tilde{F}_A(e) \neq \tilde{0}_A$ and $A \subseteq E, \tilde{F}_A(e') = \tilde{0}_A \forall e' \in E - \{e\}$. A class of all intuitionistic

fuzzy neutrosophic soft points in U is denoted as $IFNSP(U)_E$.

2) The complement of an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point $e_{\tilde{F}_A}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point $e_{\tilde{F}_A^c}$ such that $\tilde{F}_A^c(e) = (\tilde{F}_A(e))^c$

3) An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point $e_{\tilde{F}_A}$ is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{G}_A$ (or $e_{\tilde{F}_A}$) is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point of $\tilde{G}_A$, denoted $e_{\tilde{F}_A} \in \tilde{G}_A$ if for the element $e \in E, A \subseteq E, \tilde{F}_A(e) \subseteq \tilde{G}_A(e)$.

Example 2.11: Let $U = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\}$ and $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ and $A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4\}$ Then

$$e_{\tilde{F}_1} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.5, 0.6, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.4, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.6, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_4, 0.7, 0.3, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_5, 0.8, 0.2, 0.3 \rangle \}$$

$$e_{\tilde{F}_2} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.6, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.8, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_4, 0.7, 0.1, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_5, 0.8, 0.3, 0.4 \rangle \}$$

$$e_{\tilde{F}_3} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle, \langle x_4, 0.5, 0.2, 0.6 \rangle, \langle x_5, 0.7, 0.3, 0.2 \rangle \}$$

$$e_{\tilde{F}_4} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.8, 0.1, 0.4 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4 \rangle, \langle x_4, 0.4, 0.8, 0.5 \rangle, \langle x_5, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7 \rangle \}$$

The table 1 represent to the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_A$ described above.

Table 1. Tabular form of the IFNSS $\tilde{F}_A$

U	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_4
x_1	(0.5,0.6,0.3)	(0.6,0.3,0.5)	(0.7,0.4,0.3)	(0.8,0.1,0.4)
x_2	(0.4,0.7,0.2)	(0.7,0.4,0.3)	(0.6,0.1,0.2)	(0.4,0.2,0.6)
x_3	(0.6,0.2,0.3)	(0.8,0.1,0.2)	(0.7,0.2,0.5)	(0.3,0.6,0.4)
x_4	(0.7,0.3,0.2)	(0.7,0.1,0.3)	(0.5,0.2,0.6)	(0.4,0.8,0.5)
x_5	(0.8,0.2,0.3)	(0.8,0.3,0.4)	(0.7,0.3,0.2)	(0.3,0.5,0.7)

Definition 2.12 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ be two intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft sets over the common universe U . Then $\tilde{F}_A$ is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft subset of $\tilde{G}_B$ if and only if :

1. $A \subseteq B$
2. $\tilde{F}(e)$ is intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft subset of $\tilde{G}(e)$

Or $T_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x) \leq T_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x), I_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x) \leq I_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x)$,

$$F_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x) \geq F_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x), \forall e \in A, \forall x \in U$$

We denote this relationship by $\tilde{F}_A \subseteq \tilde{G}_B$ and $\tilde{F}_A$ is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft super set of $\tilde{G}_B$ if $\tilde{G}_B$ is intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft subset of $\tilde{F}_A$. We denote this relationship by $\tilde{F}_A \supseteq \tilde{G}_B$.

Example 2.13:

Let $U = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$ and $E = \{e_1, e_2\}, A = \{e_1, e_2\}$ then

$$e_{\tilde{F}_1} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.6, 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.7, 0.2, 0.5 \rangle \}$$

$$e_{\tilde{F}_2} = \{ \langle x_1, 0.8, 0.1, 0.4 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.4, 0.2, 0.6 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.4 \rangle \}$$

$$e_{\tilde{F}_1}^c = \{ \langle x_1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.2, 0.1, 0.6 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.5, 0.2, 0.7 \rangle \}$$

Let

$$\tilde{G}_A(e_1) = \{ \langle x_1, 0.8, 0.5, 0.1 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.7, 0.2, 0.1 \rangle, \langle x_3, 0.8, 0.4, 0.2 \rangle \}$$

Then $\tilde{F}_A(e_1) \subseteq \tilde{G}_B(e_1)$

i.e. $e_{\tilde{F}_1} \in \tilde{G}_A$

Theorem 2.14: If $\tilde{F}_E$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set of U . Implies

$$\tilde{F}_E = \cup \{e_{\tilde{F}} : e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E\}$$

Proof:

Let $E = \{e_i : i \in I\}$, $\tilde{F}_E$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set and $\{e_{\tilde{G}_K}\}_{K \in \Omega}$ be family of all intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point of $\tilde{F}_E$ for all $e_i \in E$ because of

$$\tilde{F}(e_i) = \cup_{K \in \Omega} \tilde{G}_K(e_i)$$

We have

$$\tilde{F}_E = \cup \{ \tilde{F}(e_i) : e_i \in E \} = \cup_{K \in \Omega} \tilde{G}_K$$

Theorem 2.15: Let $\tilde{F}_E$ and $\tilde{G}_E$ be two intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft sets in IFNSS $(U)_E$. Then $\tilde{F}(e) \subseteq \tilde{G}(e)$ if and only if $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{F}_E$ implies $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{G}_E$.

Proof:($\Rightarrow$) Let $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E$. Therefore, for all $e \in E$, $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E$. if $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{F}_E$, then $\tilde{H}(e) \subseteq \tilde{F}(e)$ because of $\tilde{H}(e) \subseteq \tilde{F}(e) \subseteq \tilde{G}(e)$ we have $\tilde{H}(e) \subseteq \tilde{G}(e)$ and so $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{G}_E$,

($\Leftarrow$): if, for every $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{F}_E$ implies $e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{G}_E$ implies the in accordance with Theorem 2.13

$\cup_{e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{F}_E} e_{\tilde{H}} = \tilde{F}_E$ and this implies

$$\cup_{e_{\tilde{H}} \in \tilde{G}_E} e_{\tilde{H}} = \tilde{G}_E. \text{ So } \tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E$$

Definition 2.16: Let $e_{\tilde{F}}$ and $e_{\tilde{G}}$ be two intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft points. For the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point $e_{\tilde{F}}$ and $e_{\tilde{G}}$ over common universe U , we say that the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft points are distinct points if $e_{\tilde{F}} \cap e_{\tilde{G}}' = 0_{\tilde{E}}$. It is clear that $e_{\tilde{F}}$ and $e_{\tilde{G}}'$ are distinct intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft points if and only if $e = e'$ or $x \neq y$.

Definition 2.17 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let U be an initial universe set. E be a set of parameters. An intuitionistic fuzzy soft topology (in short IFNST) τ on U is a family of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft sets over U satisfying the following properties:

1. $\tilde{O}_E, \tilde{I}_E \in \tau$
2. If $\tilde{F}_A, \tilde{G}_B \in \tau$, Then $\tilde{F}_A \cap \tilde{G}_B \in \tau$

3. If $\tilde{F}_{A_i} \in \tau, \forall i \in I$, I be any arbitrary index set, then $\bigcup_{i \in I} (\tilde{F}_{A_i}) \in \tau$

The triple (U, E, τ) is said to be intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space (in short IFNSTS).

Definition 2.18: Let $\hat{I}$ be a non-null collection of intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft over universe U with a fixed set of parameters E is said an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal (IFNSI for short) on U if

1. If $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ and $\tilde{G}_E \in \hat{I} \Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E \in \hat{I}$ [finite additivity]
2. $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ and $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \Rightarrow \tilde{G}_E \in \hat{I}$ [heredity].

If (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, then $(U, \tau, E, \hat{I})$ is called an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal topological space (IFNSITS for short).

Definition 2.19 [(Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ be two IFNSSs over the common universe U . Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft union of $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ denoted by $\tilde{F}_A \cup \tilde{G}_B$, and is defined as $\tilde{F}_A \cup \tilde{G}_B = \tilde{K}_C$, where $C = A \cup B$ and the truth membership, indeterminacy membership and falsity membership of $\tilde{K}_C$ are as follows.

$$T_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x) = \max(T_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), T_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x), I_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x)) \\ = \min(I_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), I_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x))$$

$$T_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x) = \min(F_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), F_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x)), \forall e \in A \cap B, \forall x \in U$$

Definition 2.20 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ be two IFNSSs over the common universe U . Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft intersection of $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ denoted by $\tilde{F}_A \cap \tilde{G}_B$ and is defined as $\tilde{F}_A \cap \tilde{G}_B = \tilde{K}_C$, where $C = A \cap B$ and the truth membership, indeterminacy membership and falsity membership of $\tilde{K}_C$ are as follows.

$$T_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x) = \min(T_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), T_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x), I_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x)) \\ = \min(I_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), I_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x))$$

$$F_{\tilde{K}(e)}(x) = \max(F_{\tilde{F}(e)}(x), F_{\tilde{G}(e)}(x)), \forall e \in A \cap B, \forall x \in U$$

Definition 2.21 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): If τ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology on U , the triple (U, E, τ) is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological spaces. Each member of τ is called an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft open set in (U, E, τ) .

An intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set is called intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closed if its complement is intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft open.

Definition 2.22 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let (U, E, τ) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological spaces. Let $\tilde{F}_A$ be an IFNSS over U . Then an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closure of $\tilde{F}_A$ denoted by $cl(\tilde{F}_A)$ and is defined as the intersection of all intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closed sets containing $\tilde{F}_A$.

$cl(\tilde{F}_A) = \bigcap \{ \tilde{G}_B : \tilde{G}_B \text{ is intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closed and } \tilde{F}_A \subseteq \tilde{G}_B \}$. It is also clear that $cl(\tilde{F}_A)$ is IFNS closed and $\tilde{F}_A \subseteq cl(\tilde{F}_A)$.

Note :

1. $cl(\tilde{O}_E) \subseteq \tilde{O}_E$ and $cl(\tilde{I}_E) \subseteq \tilde{I}_E$
2. $\tilde{F}_A$ is intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closed if and only if $\tilde{F}_A = cl(\tilde{F}_A)$
3. $cl(cl(\tilde{F}_A)) = cl(\tilde{F}_A)$.

Theorem 2.23 (Saroja, & Kalaichelvi, 2015): Let (U, E, τ) be an IFNSTS. Let $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ are two IFNSS over U . Then $cl(\tilde{F}_A \cup \tilde{G}_B) = cl(\tilde{F}_A) \cup cl(\tilde{G}_B)$

Intuitionistic Fuzzy Neutrosophic Soft Local Function and Generated Intuitionistic Fuzzy Neutrosophic Soft Ideal Topology

Definition 3.1: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space and $\hat{I}$

be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E

$$\tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau) \cup \{e_{\tilde{F}} \in \text{IFNSP}(U)_E : \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau\}$$

Is called the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft Local function of $\tilde{F}_E$ with respect to $\hat{I}$ and τ where $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}}$ is a τ -open intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set containing $e_{\tilde{F}}$.

Example 3.2:

1) If $\hat{I} = \{\tilde{0}_E\}$, then $(\tilde{F}_E)^*(\hat{I}, \tau) = \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)$ for all $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$

2) If $\hat{I} \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$, then $\tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau) = \tilde{0}_E$ for all $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$

Theorem 3.3: Let $\hat{I}_1$ and $\hat{I}_2$ be any to intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideals with the same set of parameters E on an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space (U, τ, E) .

Let $\tilde{F}_E, \tilde{G}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$. Then

- 1) $\tilde{0}_E^* = \tilde{0}_E$
- 2) $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E \implies \tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$
- 3) $\hat{I}_1 \subseteq \hat{I}_2 \implies \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_1, \tau) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_2, \tau)$
- 4) $\tilde{F}_E^* = \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^* \subseteq \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)$, where IFNScl is the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closure w.r.t. τ ,
- 5) $\tilde{F}_E^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set
- 6) $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E)^*$
- 7) $(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^* = \tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^*$
- 8) $(\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{G}_E)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^* \cap \tilde{G}_E^*$
- 9) $\tilde{H}_E \in \hat{I} \implies (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)^* = \tilde{F}_E^*$

Proof:

1) Obvious from definition 3.1 $\tilde{0}_E^* = \cup \{e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{I}_E : \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{0}_E = \tilde{0}_E \in \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau\} = \tilde{0}_E$

2) Let $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*$. Then $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$. Since $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E \implies \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{G}_E$ and $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}$. Then $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{G}_E \in \hat{I}$

, $\forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$ from definition 3.1. Hence $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{G}_E^*$, Thus $\tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$.

3) Let $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_2, \tau)$. Then $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}_2, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$. Since $\hat{I}_1 \subseteq \hat{I}_2$. Then $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}_1 \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$. Hence $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_1, \tau)$.

Thus $\tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_2, \tau) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}_1, \tau)$.

4) Since $\tilde{0}_E \subseteq \hat{I}$ for any IFNS ideal on U , therefore by (3) and example (3.2)

$$\tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*(\tilde{0}_E, \tau) = \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E) \text{ for any IFNSS}(\tilde{F}_E) \text{ on } U.$$

Suppose, $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^*$ so for every $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}}$ open IFNS set contains $e_{\tilde{F}}$

$\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E^* \neq \tilde{0}_E$, there exist $e_{\tilde{G}_1} \in \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E^*$ such that for every $\tilde{V}_{E,e_{\tilde{G}_1}}$ open IFNS set contains $e_{\tilde{G}_1}$, $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}$. Since $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{V}_{E,e_{\tilde{G}_1}}$ open IFNS set contain $e_{\tilde{G}_1}$ then

$$(\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{V}_{E,e_{\tilde{G}_1}}) \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I} \text{ which ideal to } \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$$

Therefore $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*$ and so $\text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*$ and since $\tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^*$. Hence $\text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^* = (\tilde{F}_E^*)^*$.

5) From (4) $\text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E)^* = (\tilde{F}_E^*)^*$ then $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set.

6) By (4), we have

$$(\tilde{F}_E^*)^* = \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq \text{IFNScl}(\tilde{F}_E^*) = \tilde{F}_E^*$$

7) Let $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^*$. Then $\{e_{\tilde{F}} \in \text{IFNSP}(U)_E; \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E) \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau\}$, i.e. $(\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E) \cup (\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{G}_E) \notin \hat{I}$

$\hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$, then we have two case $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}$ or the converse $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{G}_E \notin \hat{I}$

By definition 3.1

$\{e_{\tilde{F}} \in \text{IFSP}(U)_E; \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau\}$ or $\{e_{\tilde{F}} \in \text{IFSP}(U)_E; \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{G}_E \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau\} \Rightarrow e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^*$. Therefore $(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^*$.

Again, we have $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E$ and $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E$ from (2) we have $\tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^*$ and $\tilde{G}_E^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^*$

Hence $\tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^*$ and it is implies that $(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^* = \tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^*$

8) We have $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E$ and $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E$. Therefore $(\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{G}_E)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^* \cap \tilde{G}_E^*$

9) Let $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)^*$. Then $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E) \notin \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$, i.e. $(\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E) \cup (\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{H}_E) \notin \hat{I} \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$, then we have two case $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ and $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{H}_E \notin \hat{I}$ or the converse, if $\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{H}_E \notin \hat{I}$ gives $\tilde{H}_E \notin \hat{I}$ which is a contradiction. Thus

$\tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E,e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau$. So $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*$ hence $(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*$ for the reverse inclusion, since $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)$ then $\tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)^*$ from (2) hence $(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{H}_E)^* = \tilde{F}_E^*$.

Definition 3.4: Let (U, E, τ) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space and $\hat{I}$ to be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E . Then the operator $\text{IFNScl}^*: \text{IFNSS}(U)_E \rightarrow \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ defined by: $\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E) = \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closure operator.

Theorem 3.5:

- 1) $\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{0}_E) = \tilde{0}_E$
- 2) $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E), \forall \tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$

$$3) \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E) = \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E) \cup \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{G}_E)$$

$$4) \text{IFNScl}^*(\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)) \subseteq \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E), \forall \tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$$

Proof:

$$1) \text{ Since } \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{0}_E) = \tilde{0}_E \cup \tilde{0}_E^* = \tilde{0}_E \cup \tilde{0}_E = \tilde{0}_E \text{ from theorem 3.7(1)}$$

$$2) \text{ Since } \tilde{F}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^* = \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E) \text{ Thus } \tilde{F}_E \subseteq \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)$$

$$3) \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E) = (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E) \cup (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E)^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E) \cup (\tilde{F}_E^* \cup \tilde{G}_E^*) = (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) \cup (\tilde{G}_E \cup \tilde{G}_E^*) = \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E) \cup \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{G}_E) \text{ from theorem 3.7 (7)}$$

$$4) \text{IFNScl}^*(\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)) = \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) = ((\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) \cup (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*))^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) \cup \tilde{F}_E^* \cup (\tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) \cup (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*) = (\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^*)$$

$$= \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E) \text{ from theorem 3.7 (6), (7),}$$

$$\text{Thus } \text{IFNScl}^*(\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)) \subseteq \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)$$

Definition 3.6: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E and $\text{IFNScl}^*: \text{IFNSS}(U)_E \rightarrow \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ be the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft closure operator. then there exist a unique intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology over U with the same set of parameters E , finer than τ , called τ^* - intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology, denoted by $\tau^*(\hat{I})$ or τ^* given by $\tau^*(\hat{I}) = \{\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E: \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c\}$.

Example 3.7: Let $U = \{x_1, x_2\}$ and $E = \{e\}$ and $\tau = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, \tilde{F}_E\}$ where $\tilde{F}_E$ is an

intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set over U defined by

$$\tilde{F}_E = \{ \langle x_1, 0.4, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1, 0.8, 0.3 \rangle \}$$

Then τ defines an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology on U.

Let $\hat{I} = \{ \tilde{O}_E, \tilde{G}_E \}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U where $\tilde{G}_E$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set over U defined by $\tilde{G}(e) = \{ \langle x_1, 0.4, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1, 0.8, 0.3 \rangle \}$

Then, $\tau^* = \{ \tilde{O}_E, \tilde{I}_E, \tilde{F}_{1E}, \tilde{F}_{2E} \}$ where $\tilde{F}_{1E}, \tilde{F}_{2E}$ are intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft sets over U where

$$\tilde{F}_{1E}(e) = \{ \langle x_1, 0.4, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.1, 0.8, 0.3 \rangle \}$$

$$\tilde{F}_{2E}(e) = \{ \langle x_1, 0.2, 0.7, 0.1 \rangle, \langle x_2, 0.3, 0.8, 0.1 \rangle \}$$

Example 3.8:

1) If $\hat{I} = \{ \tilde{O}_E \}$, then $IFNScl^*(\tilde{F}_E) = IFNScl(\tilde{F}_E)$ for all $(\tilde{F}_E) \in IFNSS(U)_E$ and $\tau = \tau^*$

2) If $\hat{I} = IFNSS(U)_E$, then $IFNScl^*(\tilde{F}_E) = \tilde{F}_E$ for all $\tilde{F}_E \in IFNSS(U)_E$ and $\tau^* = IFNSS(U)_E$ (the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft discrete topology).

Definition 3.9: Let $\tilde{F}_A, \tilde{G}_B$ be two Intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft sets over X. We define the difference of $\tilde{F}_A$ and $\tilde{G}_B$ as the intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft $\tilde{H}_C$ written as $\tilde{F}_A - \tilde{G}_B = \tilde{H}_C$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $e \in C, x \in X$

$$\mu_{H(e)}(x) = \min(\mu_{F(e)}(x), \nu_{G(e)}(x)) \quad \text{and} \\ \nu_{H(e)}(x) = \max(\nu_{F(e)}(x), \mu_{G(e)}(x)).$$

$$\tilde{F}_A - \tilde{G}_B = \tilde{F}_A \cap \tilde{G}_B^c$$

$$\min(T_{F(e)}(x), T_{G(e)}(x)), I_{F(e)}(x) = I_{G(e)}(x), \max(F_{F(e)}(x), F_{G(e)}(x)), \forall e \in C, \forall x \in X$$

Theorem 3.10: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space and $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E. Then

$$B(\hat{I}, \tau) = \{ \tilde{F}_E - \tilde{G}_E : \tilde{F}_E \in \tau, \tilde{G}_E \in \hat{I} \}$$

Forms a basis for generated intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology $\tau^*(\hat{I})$.

Proof:

Since $\tilde{I}_E \in \tau, \tilde{O}_E \in \hat{I}$. Then

$\tilde{I}_E - \tilde{O}_E \in B$. Hence $\tilde{I}_E \in B$ and

$$\bigcup_{j \in \tau} (\tilde{F}_{jE} - \tilde{G}_{jE}) = \tilde{I}_E$$

Also, Let $((\tilde{F}_{1E} - \tilde{G}_{1E}), (\tilde{F}_{2E} - \tilde{G}_{2E})) \in B$ such that

$$e_{\tilde{F}} \in ((\tilde{F}_{1E} - \tilde{G}_{1E}) \cap (\tilde{F}_{2E} - \tilde{G}_{2E}))$$

Then

$$e_{\tilde{F}} \in ((\tilde{F}_{1E} - \tilde{G}_{1E}) \cap (\tilde{F}_{2E} - \tilde{G}_{2E})) \\ = ((\tilde{F}_{1E} \cap \tilde{G}_{1E}^c) \cap (\tilde{F}_{2E} \cap \tilde{G}_{2E}^c)) \\ = ((\tilde{F}_{1E} \cap \tilde{F}_{2E}) \cap (\tilde{G}_{1E}^c \cap \tilde{G}_{2E}^c)) \\ = (\tilde{F}_{1E} \cap \tilde{F}_{2E}) \cap (\tilde{G}_{1E} \cup \tilde{G}_{2E})^c \\ = (\tilde{F}_{1E} \cap \tilde{F}_{2E}) - (\tilde{G}_{1E} \cap \tilde{G}_{2E}) \in B(\hat{I}, \tau)$$

Thus, B is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft basis of τ^* .

Corollary 3.11: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space and $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E. Then

$$\tau \subseteq B(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq \tau^*(\hat{I})$$

Proof: Let $\tilde{F}_E \in \tau$, since $\tilde{O}_E \in \hat{I}$

Thus

$$\tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E - \tilde{O}_E \in B(\hat{I}, \tau) \text{ i.e}$$

$$\tilde{F}_E \in B(\hat{I}, \tau)$$

So, $\tau \subseteq B(\hat{I}, \tau)$, and since $B(\hat{I}, \tau)$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft basis of $\tau^*(\hat{I})$, then $B(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq \tau^*(\hat{I})$

Hence

$$\tau \subseteq B(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq \tau^*(\hat{I})$$

Theorem 3.12: Let $\hat{I}_1$ and $\hat{I}_2$ are an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideals over U , $\hat{I}_1 \subseteq \hat{I}_2$ then $\tau^*(\hat{I}_1) \subseteq \tau^*(\hat{I}_2)$.

Proof:

$$\text{Let } \tilde{F}_E \in \tau^*(\hat{I}_1) \rightarrow \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c \cup (\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau) \\ = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$$

From definition 3.10

$$\Rightarrow (\tilde{F}_E^c)^c = [(\tilde{F}_E)^c \cup ((\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau))]^c$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau)$$

Since $\hat{I}_1 \subseteq \hat{I}_2$ then $(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq ((\tilde{F}_E)^c)^*(\hat{I}_1, \tau)$

From theorem 3.7(3)

$$\Rightarrow [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_1, \tau) \subseteq [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_2, \tau)$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_1, \tau) \\ \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_2, \tau)$$

But $\tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_2, \tau) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E$

So $\tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}_2, \tau)$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E^c \cup ((\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}_2, \tau)) = \tilde{F}_E^c$$

Thus $\text{IFNScl}^*(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$ i.e

$$\tilde{F}_E \in \tau^*(\hat{I}_2),$$

Hence $\tau^*(\hat{I}_1) \subseteq \tau^*(\hat{I}_2)$.

Theorem 3.13: Let τ_1, τ_2 be two intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topologies on U . Then for any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal $\hat{I}$ on U , $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$ implies $\tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_2) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1) \forall \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ and $\tau_1^* \subseteq \tau_2^*$

Proof:

$$\text{Let } e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau_2$$

Since $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \notin \hat{I}, \forall \tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \in \tau_2,$$

Thus $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1)$ hence

$$\tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_2) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1)$$

Next, we proved $\tau_1^* \subseteq \tau_2^*$, let $\tilde{F}_E \in \tau_1^* \rightarrow \text{IFNScl}^*_{\tau_1}(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$

$$\Rightarrow \text{IFNScl}^*_{\tau_1}(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c \cup (\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1) \\ = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$$

From definition 3.10

$$\Rightarrow (\tilde{F}_E^c)^c = [(\tilde{F}_E)^c \cup ((\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1))]^c$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_1)$$

Since $\tau_1 \subseteq \tau_2$ then

$(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau_2) \subseteq ((\tilde{F}_E)^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau_1)$ from above

$$\Rightarrow [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_1) \subseteq [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_2)$$

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_1) \\ \subseteq \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_2)$$

But $\tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_2) \subseteq \tilde{F}_E$

So $\tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap [(\tilde{F}_E^c)^*]^c(\hat{I}, \tau_2)$,

$$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E^c \cup (\tilde{F}_E^c)^*(\hat{I}, \tau_2) = \tilde{F}_E^c$$

Thus $\text{IFNScl}^*_{\tau_2}(\tilde{F}_E)^c = (\tilde{F}_E)^c$ i.e

$$\tilde{F}_E \in \tau^*(\hat{I}_2).$$

Compatibility of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Neutrosophic Soft Ideals with Intuitionistic Fuzzy Neutrosophic Soft Topology

Definition 4.1: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space and $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U . τ is said to be compatible with $\hat{I}$, denoted by $\tau \sim \hat{I}$, if for every intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_E$ of U and for all intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft point $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E$, there exists $\tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}}$ open intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic contains $e_{\tilde{F}}$ such that $\tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$, then $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$.

Theorem 4.2: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal

over U with the same set of parameters E and $\tau \sim \hat{I}$. Then for any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_E$ of U .

$$\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E \text{ implies } \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O} \text{ iff}$$

$$\tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^*$$

Proof:

($\Rightarrow$) suppose that $\tilde{F}_E$ any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set of U ,

$$\tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* \text{ and } \tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$$

$$\text{Then } \tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* = \tilde{O}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$$

$$\text{Hence } \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$$

($\Leftarrow$) suppose that $\tilde{F}_E$ any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set of U ,

$$\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E \text{ and } \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E. \text{ Since } \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E \text{ and } \tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$$

$$\Rightarrow (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* = (\tilde{O}_E)^* = \tilde{O}_E$$

$$\text{Hence } \tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^*$$

Corollary 4.3: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E , for any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{F}_E$ of U and $\tau \sim \hat{I}$. Then $\tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E^*)^*$

Proof:

suppose that $\tilde{F}_E$ any intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set of U ,

$$\text{Since } \tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^* \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^* = (\tilde{F}_E^*)^*$$

$$\text{From theorem 3.7 (8), (6). Thus } \tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E^*)^*.$$

Theorem 4.4: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E . Then the following are equivalent:

(a) $\tau \sim \hat{I}$

(b) or every $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ such that $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$

(c) or every $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ such that $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$.

Proof:

(a) $\Rightarrow$ (b) Let $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ such that $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$ then $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$, so $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$

Since $\tilde{F}_E^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set, then for all $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E$ and $e_{\tilde{F}} \notin \tilde{F}_E^*$ such that $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$, we have $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ for some $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \in \tau$.

Thus $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ by (a)

(b) $\Rightarrow$ (c) Let $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$. Since $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$ then $(\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c) \cap (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c) \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^* \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c) \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$

Then $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$ by (b)

$e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E, (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ such that $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$

$\Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$. Since $\tilde{F}_E^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set.

$\Rightarrow (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \in \tau$. Thus $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ by (b).

(c) $\Rightarrow$ (a) suppose that $\tilde{F}_E \in \text{IFNSS}(U)_E$ and assume that for every $e_{\tilde{F}} \in \tilde{F}_E$ there exist $\tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}} \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$ and $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$.

Then $e_{\tilde{F}} \notin \tilde{F}_E^*$ such that $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E$. Hence $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$.

Since $\tilde{F}_E^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \in \tau$ such that $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$. Let $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^c = \tilde{Q}_{E, e_{\tilde{F}}}$

Such that $e_{\tilde{F}} \in (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c$. Thus $(\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \cap \tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$. Since $\tilde{F}_E \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c \Rightarrow \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E \cap (\tilde{F}_E^*)^c = \tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^*$

By hypothesis, $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$. Thus $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$. Hence $\tau \sim \hat{I}$.

Theorem 4.5: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be

an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E . Then for every $\tilde{F}_E \in IFNSS(U)_E$, $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$ if and only if $\tilde{F}_E$ contains no non-null soft set $\tilde{G}_E$ with $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$, then $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$

Proof:

($\Rightarrow$) suppose that $\tilde{F}_E \in IF$ such that $\tilde{F}_E$ contains no non null intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{G}_E$ with $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$ and $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$. Since $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^*$ from theorem 4.2. It follows that $\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^*$. By assumption

$$\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{O}_E, \text{ Thus } \tilde{F}_E = \tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}.$$

($\Leftarrow$) suppose that $\tilde{F}_E \in IFNSS(U)_E$ such that $\tilde{F}_E$ contains no non null intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{G}_E$ with $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$ and $\tilde{F}_E \in \hat{I}$. Since $(\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^*) \cap (\tilde{F}_E \cap \tilde{F}_E^*)^* = \tilde{O}_E$ and $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^*$ contains no non null intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set $\tilde{G}_E$ with $\tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{G}_E^*$. Hence $\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$.

Theorem 4.6: If (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E and compatible τ .

Then an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set is τ^* -closed if and only if it is the union of τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set and an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set in $\hat{I}$.

Proof:

Let $\tilde{F}_E$ be a τ^* -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set. Then $IFNScl^*(\tilde{F}_E) = \tilde{F}_E$ and $\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{F}_E$. Hence $\tilde{F}_E^* \subseteq \tilde{F}_E$. Thus

$$\tilde{F}_E = (\tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^*) \cup \tilde{F}_E^*, \quad \tilde{F}_E - \tilde{F}_E^* \in \hat{I}$$

from 4.4 $\tilde{F}_E^*$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set from theorem 3.7(5)

Conversely, let $\tilde{F}_E = (\tilde{G}_E \cup \tilde{I}_E)$, where $\tilde{G}_E$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set and $\tilde{I}_E \in \hat{I}$.

Then $\tilde{F}_E^* = (\tilde{G}_E \cup \tilde{I}_E)^* = \tilde{G}_E^* \subseteq IFNScl(\tilde{G}_E) = \tilde{G}_E \subseteq \tilde{F}_E$ from theorem 3.7(2)(4).

Hence $\tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{F}_E^* = \tilde{F}_E$. Thus $IFNScl^*(\tilde{F}_E) = \tilde{F}_E$. It follows that $\tilde{F}_E$ is τ^* -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set.

Theorem 4.7: Let (U, τ, E) be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topological space, $\hat{I}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft ideal over U with the same set of parameters E . If $\tau \sim \hat{I}$ then $B(\hat{I}, \tau)$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft topology and hence $B = \tau^*$.

Proof:

Let $\tilde{G}_E \in \tau^*$. Then $\tilde{G}_E^c = \tilde{F}_E \cup \tilde{I}_E$, where $\tilde{F}_E$ is τ -closed intuitionistic fuzzy neutrosophic soft set and $\tilde{I}_E \in \hat{I}$.

Hence $\tilde{G}_E = \tilde{F}_E^c \cap \tilde{I}_E^c = \tilde{F}_E^c - \tilde{I}_E$, where $\tilde{F}_E \in \tau$ and $\tilde{I}_E \in \hat{I}$. Thus $\tilde{G}_E = \tilde{F}_E^c - \tilde{I}_E \in B(\hat{I}, \tau)$. So $\tau^* \subseteq B(\hat{I}, \tau)$

And since $B(\hat{I}, \tau) \subseteq \tau^*$ from corollary 3.14 hence $B = \tau^*$.

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